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Evaluation Method of Student Achievement Levels

Project-Based ICT Education through Citizen Support System Development

Mikiko Sode Tanaka

International College of Technology

Kanazawa, Japan

E-mail: sode@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

Takao Ito

Kanazawa Institute of Technology

Nonoichi, Japan

E-mail: ito@neptune.kanazawa-it.ac.jp

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INTRODUCTION

One of the difficulties in ICT education through regular lessons is that educators must teach all system development techniques within a limited timeframe, despite the fact that students cannot learn without actually experiencing these techniques. To solve this problem, we conducted an industry-university collaboration project to develop a citizen support system as an extracurricular activity. The project was supported as a Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications IoT Service Creation Support Project [1]. The purposes of the IoT Service Creation Support Project is to identify specific problems to overcome when creating and deploying IoT services through demonstration projects, build a reference model to solve these issues, and promote data utilisation. Students developed a citizen support system through University-Business cooperation [2]. Through this activity, students learned about entrepreneurship.

To confirm students' growth, we investigated a method to evaluate student achievement in software development education through collaboration between industry and the community. This paper describes the evaluation method. The proposed evaluation method ensures that students understand the contents of the curriculum by expressing these contents and evaluating the skills they acquired at certain activity milestones. In addition, the teacher evaluated students using the same indicator and encouraged them to acquire missing abilities. We think this method confirms students' growth by determining whether individual evaluation results for each grade are effective.

1 FEATURES OF THE BUS STOP PROJECT

1.1 What is the bus stop project

At Kanazawa Institute of Technology (KIT), students are educated through curricular and extracurricular education. The Project Design Program (PD) is the backbone of curricular education, and carried out as a regular class for all students. It has made great progress [3-4]. Project-Based Learning (PBL) is employed in PD courses.

Extracurricular activities also play an important role at KIT. They include the YUMEKOBO Projects (YUMEKOBO is a Japanese term that refers to the Factory for Dreams and Ideas), department/lab-related programs, collaboration programs with industry and the community, and internship programs. In these activities, students set their own objectives and learn from their successes and failures. For example, the YUMEKOBO Projects are self-directed to develop students' technical competence [5]. There were 16 YUMEKOBO Projects in 2016 [6]. The education project described in this paper was implemented as an extracurricular activity.

The purpose of the bus stop project is to increase software development abilities and cultivate students' problem-solving skills by developing an ICT system for citizen support. The system developed is designed to contribute to the revitalisation of the city and improve civic life. With the cooperation of Nonoichi-City, this project included many activities. Furthermore, local companies cooperated in developing the system. We targeted Nonoichi City, where the university is located, and tackled the issue of improving civic life, because students who are citizens consider it meaningful to solve their own civic problems and enrich the lives of others.

Our project was adopted by the Ministry of Internal Affairs' 'IoT Service Creation Support Project', and a demonstration experiment of a smart bus stop was performed in Nonoichi City. To ensure the success of the project, we developed a system in collaboration with parties who were able to meet a few times. Students must have the ability to develop programs without bugs according to a schedule set in collaboration with a company. Students were required to acquire new skills. *Fig. 1* provides an overview of the developed system.

Fig. 1. Citizen support system for Nonoichi City

1.2 Flow of the project activity

We believed that by designing and implementing the project with an entrepreneurial spirit, rather than as set out previously, we would acquire more useful skills for society. Therefore, our curriculum combines entrepreneurship education such as the construction of a business model and CDIO education, based on the abilities to 'conceive, design, implement, and operate' (Fig. 2) [7, 8, 9]. The flow of system development education for the bus stop project is as follows. We constructed the flow based on the system development flow of this enterprise [10].

- 1) Planning: 'Assembling the concept'
- 2) Planning: 'Building a business model'
- 3) Proposal: 'Create a business plan'
- 4) System design and construction
- 5) Introduction/deployment
- 6) Operation and maintenance

This provided a mechanism by which to learn the abovementioned process over the course of a few years. Students cannot learn the entire flow in four years, and depending on the year of admission, cannot learn it in order starting from Phase 1. The size of the project group is about five people in a general enterprise, and the project is carried out over a period of six months to a year. As the students change each year, it is structured to take place over six years, and learning occurs through the activities carried out for three or four hours once a week. We are currently in Phases 3 and 4, and considering the process of commercialisation.

Fig. 2. Requirements of CDIO [9]

For software development, various indirect management tasks are required to create the work directly related to developing software such as request analysis, design, implementation, and testing, as well as other planned work. As the scale increases, so does the importance and weight of such management work. In software engineering, a project is defined as periodic work carried out to create unique products, services, and products [11]. The goal is to reach the deadline within the cost and resource constraints set for the project. We believe that developing the ability to develop software with limited time, costs, and resources is an important factor in education in the field; thus, we carried out activities involved in the project in this phase.

The major difference from regular lesson classes is that we develop the practice of keeping pace with the citizens and city officials who are customers and with cooperating companies. We must manage the requirements, cost, and time constraints of customers at the company level. To ensure the success of the project, we must plan and implement it appropriately. For example, one must plan what to do day by day to achieve the final goal. To do so within the prescribed time and cost, one must plan and implement according to how much time and cost each factor requires. We must avoid time and cost overruns and ensure the project achieves its goal. In addition, as students execute the project, teachers must consider student human factors and develop members' abilities accordingly.

2 EVALUATING THE ACHIEVEMENT OF PARTICIPATING STUDENTS

2.1 Achievement evaluation items

Society is constantly changing, noticeably so in the information processing field. We believe that the ability to respond flexibly to this change, the creation of new value, and ability to lead society in a better direction are important. We believe we should actively tackle social issues and focus on developing human resources able to improve society. Based on this philosophy, we are developing regional innovation systems through community collaboration as extracurricular activities.

We posited the following three requirements for becoming a global leader, and the aim is that students acquire these abilities.

- A) Recognition/comprehension to cope with social change

B) Power to change one's own interests and abilities into actual behaviour

C) Spirit and power to fully utilise one's own resources and solve social problems

Another project purpose was to develop software development capability through developing an ICT system for citizen support. By providing education on the system design method while creating the system, we aimed to improve students' skills as information processing engineers.

The skills necessary for ICT and IoT engineers have been defined [12, 13]. In this project, because it focuses on educating undergraduate students, we assessed the degree of accomplishment by evaluating the basic knowledge and management abilities needed for system design. To nurture global leaders, a sub-work leader was assigned to fourth year undergraduate students, who had to compete a paper in English. Evaluation was based on whether the sub-work was successfully completed and the paper submitted and successfully presented.

2.2 Achievement evaluation method

Evaluation by students is subjective. Evaluation by a teacher should be according to an absolute index, but this is difficult, because different work is performed every year. Therefore, we evaluated whether each work activity was completed or not. For example, for programming language skills, we evaluated whether the section allocated was completed. The difficulty of the program differs depending on the section allocated; however, the program difficulty was not evaluated. In addition, in some cases, it was completed with the help of other members, and even if not completed through one person's abilities, we evaluated the success thereof. We thought it was important to understand the flow as the first step. Likewise, to evaluate management ability, the teacher instructed students to engage in management activities. However, in many cases, management was not well done. In these cases, the teacher provided detailed instructions or took over the managing activities. In this case, we also evaluated that student managed. In this way, we made an evaluation on the undergraduate students, focusing on understanding and experiencing the flow.

Evaluation by the teacher is told to the student verbally. At the same time, the list of work to be done next and the reason are reported. The teacher chooses and recommends the work that is best for the growth of the students from the next work to do. At the same time, we need to allocate personnel who do not inconvenience to companies that are cooperating. Because the project is not a class, students do not have to accept teachers' recommendations. Students will consider the advice of the teacher and decide what to do next for themselves. We believe that deciding by themselves increases their abilities. For that reason, we prioritize student selection and decide personnel assignment. Thus, there are many situations where teachers themselves have to work on their own. We believe that we must accept it.

3 EVALUATION RESULTS OF THE DEGREE OF ACHIEVEMENT

Some evaluation results are shown in *Table 1* and *Table 2*. We conducted a questionnaire survey on participating students as a self-assessment. The questionnaire determined the extent to which students' ability for system design developed through participating in the project. Questionnaires were received for 4 first-grade students, 13 second-grade students, 8 third-grade students, and 3 fourth-grade students. *Table 1* and *Table 2* show some of the items evaluated. *Table 1* provides the evaluation items for the basic knowledge necessary for system design, and *Table 2* those for the required management abilities. Both teachers and students conducted the evaluation.

Table 1. Basic knowledge necessary for system design

	First Grade	Second Grade	Third Grade	Fourth Grade	Teacher
Programming language skills	4	10	8	3	5
Hardware, software basic knowledge	4	8	5	2	20
Testing, debugging skills	0	3	3	3	3
Database technology skills	0	2	0	1	5
Security skills	0	3	1	1	2
System design skills	0	6	1	2	10
System requirements definition skill	0	1	2	1	10
Network, communication technology skills	0	4	3	1	15
Technical analysis, analysis skills	0	1	2	2	10
System maintenance operation skills	0	0	2	1	3

Table 2. Management ability necessary for system design

	Student	Teacher
Progress management ability for the entire project	11	11
Accurate instructions to program personnel	9	11
Distribution of work, personnel adjustment	11	11
Collateral of system quality	3	5
Ability to write documents such as design documents	10	11

Fig. 3. Presentation at an international conference [14]

We discuss the results of the evaluation in 2017 of the bus stop project. We conducted a questionnaire survey on participants' ability to acquire the required skills for system design through participating in the project. In response to the question on whether programming ability improved, 89% of students responded that it had. Furthermore, 38% said that their management abilities for the project improved. Regarding client's requests, 50% of the students heard these requests, and indicated that the ability to build a better trust relationship improved. In addition, 68% responded that their ability to work smoothly with project members improved. We received positive feedback from

students that they were able to learn practical contents and were good at participating in the project. Based on the results of the questionnaire survey, we confirmed the effectiveness of our education system. In addition, students were able to summarise and present the results as papers [14, 15]. We believe these skills are important in becoming a global leader. A presentation is shown in *Fig. 3*.

4 CONCLUSION

It is difficult to evaluate the outcomes of extracurricular activities, because there is no fixed curriculum. However, to encourage students' growth, we must see students' growth and encourage the next step in this development process. To confirm students' growth, we investigated a method to evaluate student achievement in software development education through collaboration between industry and the community. We also evaluated this. This paper described the evaluation method and results thereof. The evaluation method of the proposal ensures that students understand the contents of the curriculum by expressing these contents, and self-evaluating the skills they acquired at certain activity milestones. In addition, the teacher evaluates students with the same indicator and encourages them to acquire missing abilities. The proposed method is an effective method for student growth in that students understand the goals of the curriculum, make goals, implement and evaluate themselves. Also, we think that evaluation from the teacher and advice of goal setting is effective and helps the growth of the student. Therefore, the proposed evaluation method is considered to be effective.

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